

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SEMI-MILITARY SCHOOL CULTURE IN SHAPING STUDENTS' DISCIPLINE CHARACTER FOR IMPROVING GRADUATE QUALITY IN VOCATIONAL HIGH SCHOOLS

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Abstract. *SMK Negeri 2 Sangatta Utara has a unique school culture characterized by a semi-military approach to instill student discipline. This study aims to describe the planning, organizing, implementation, and evaluation of the semi-military culture in forming the cadets' discipline character to improve educational quality at SMK Negeri 2 Sangatta Utara. This research employs a qualitative approach with a case study method. Data collection techniques include observation, in-depth interviews, and documentation, with data validity checked through source and method triangulation. The research findings indicate that the planning stage includes the beginning of the school year meetings, needs and environmental analysis, development of military programs and their integration into the curriculum, organizing extracurricular activities, and compiling control books for students and parents. The implementation stage includes the beret ceremony during orientation, routine morning and evening assemblies, providing action guidance per the Disciplinary Committee SOP, recording points in the Cadet Violation Card, recording achievements in the Cadet Achievement Card, conducting character development activities, providing students with control books as a guide for implementing discipline, and giving parents control books to monitor student discipline at home. The implementation of a semi-military culture at SMK Negeri 2 Sangatta Utara has been carried out with a systematic and structured approach through comprehensive planning, organizing, implementation, and evaluation. An effective semi-military culture fosters student discipline, responsibility, and leadership skills, ultimately enhancing graduate quality and their readiness for the workforce or further education.*

Keywords: *Semi-Military Culture, Student Discipline, Vocational High Schools, Graduate Quality*

Abstrak. SMK Negeri 2 Sangatta Utara memiliki budaya sekolah yang unik, ditandai dengan pendekatan semi-militer untuk menanamkan disiplin siswa. Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk menggambarkan perencanaan, pengorganisasian, pelaksanaan, dan evaluasi budaya semi-militer dalam membentuk karakter disiplin cadet untuk meningkatkan kualitas pendidikan di SMK Negeri 2 Sangatta Utara. Penelitian ini menggunakan pendekatan kualitatif dengan metode studi kasus. Teknik pengumpulan data mencakup observasi, wawancara mendalam, dan dokumentasi, dengan validitas data diperiksa melalui triangulasi sumber dan metode. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa tahap perencanaan mencakup rapat awal tahun ajaran, analisis kebutuhan dan lingkungan, pengembangan program militer dan integrasinya ke dalam kurikulum, pengorganisasian kegiatan ekstrakurikuler, dan penyusunan buku kontrol untuk siswa dan orang tua. Tahap pelaksanaan mencakup upacara beret selama orientasi, apel rutin pagi dan sore, memberikan panduan tindakan sesuai dengan SOP Komite Disiplin, mencatat poin dalam Kartu Pelanggaran Cadet, mencatat prestasi dalam Kartu Prestasi Cadet,

melaksanakan kegiatan pengembangan karakter, memberikan buku kontrol kepada siswa sebagai panduan pelaksanaan disiplin, dan memberikan buku kontrol kepada orang tua untuk memantau disiplin siswa di rumah. Pelaksanaan budaya semi-militer di SMK Negeri 2 Sangatta Utara telah dilaksanakan dengan pendekatan yang sistematis dan terstruktur melalui perencanaan, pengorganisasian, pelaksanaan, dan evaluasi yang komprehensif. Budaya semi-militer yang efektif mendorong disiplin siswa, tanggung jawab, dan keterampilan kepemimpinan, yang pada akhirnya meningkatkan kualitas pendidikan.

Kata Kunci: Budaya Semi-Militer, Disiplin Siswa, Sekolah Menengah Kejuruan (SMK), Kualitas Lulusan

INTRODUCTION

Vocational High Schools (SMK) play a strategic role in producing a workforce that is ready to compete in the business and industrial sectors. SMKs are expected to produce graduates with both technical competencies and soft skills that align with labor market demands. However, in reality, there remains a gap between the skills possessed by SMK graduates and the needs of the workforce, particularly in terms of discipline and work ethic. A study conducted by Nurjanah et al (2022) revealed that 60% of companies in the manufacturing industry sector in Indonesia reported that SMK graduates still lack discipline, teamwork skills, and communication abilities (Nurjanah et al., 2022). This finding aligns with an earlier study by Nugroho (2022), which highlighted that the lack of discipline development among SMK students is a major factor hindering their ability to adapt to dynamic and demanding work environments (Nugroho, 2022). Another study by Arif et al (2021) also emphasized that although the SMK curriculum is designed to prepare students for the workforce, its implementation often falls short in developing soft skills, including discipline and work ethic (Arif et al., 2021). Factors such as the lack of good role models, minimal implementation of a disciplined school culture, and limited extracurricular activities that support character development are among the primary causes. This conclusion is reinforced by Widayana who pointed out that a school culture that does not sufficiently support the formation of disciplined character remains one of the biggest challenges in preparing SMK students for the workforce (Widayana, 2023). Thus, the gap between the quality of SMK graduates and the needs of the workforce is not merely a technical issue but also involves behavioral and attitudinal aspects that must be addressed through a more comprehensive and integrative educational approach. SMKN 2 Sangatta Utara, like many other vocational schools, faces challenges related to the employability of its graduates in the industrial sector.

Table 1. Employment Absorption Data of SMK N 2 Sangatta Utara Alumni

No	Year	Number of Graduates	Employment Absorption	Higher Education Absorption	Entrepreneurship	Not Recorded
1	2016	325	89	38	25	162
2	2017	325	93	56	15	157
3	2018	312	100	65	10	150
4	2019	312	182	75	5	50
5	2020	313	65	20	-	228
6	2021	321	78	15	-	228
7	2022	321	250	37	7	27
8	2023	325	284	27	14	-

Source: SMKN 2 Sangatta Utara Document, 2024

Based on student absorption data since 2016 as presented in table 1, when the semi-military culture was first implemented, it can be observed that the number of students absorbed into the workforce remained low. An increase occurred as the implementation of the semi-military culture at school became more established. However, in 2020, absorption rates declined again due to the COVID-19 pandemic in 2019, which forced learning activities to be

conducted online from students' homes (Hajar et al., 2023). As a result, students were unable to practice discipline as they would have in school, leading to a decline in the discipline character they were expected to develop. Research conducted by Anggraini et al (2022) revealed that one of the main reasons for this low absorption rate is the lack of student discipline (Anggraini et al., 2022).

This weak discipline makes graduates less capable of adhering to workplace regulations and demands, causing many companies to be reluctant to recruit them after their internship period ends. Additionally, Ali et al (2020) in their study, highlighted that the mismatch between graduate quality and industry standards is a major obstacle to improving the quality of vocational education (Ali et al., 2020). The study indicates that vocational school graduates often lack the work ethic and discipline required, making them unable to meet industry expectations. Both studies emphasize the importance of integrating character and discipline development programs into the vocational school curriculum to bridge the gap between education and industry needs (Irfansyah et al., 2023; Sawaliyah, 2022).

To address the challenge of low graduate absorption in the industrial sector, SMKN 2 Sangatta Utara has adopted a unique strategy by implementing a school culture characterized by a semi-military system. A semi-military system refers to an organization, structure, or activity that incorporates certain military characteristics but is not fully part of the official military. This approach was chosen in response to the urgent need to enhance student discipline, which is considered crucial in preparing them for the workforce. Research by Hidayatullah et al (2020) shows that the application of semi-military discipline in an educational environment, particularly through extracurricular programs, can significantly improve student discipline levels (Hidayatullah et al., 2020). This program focuses not only on physical training but also on strengthening mental and behavioral attributes that align with workplace demands. Furthermore, Siburian et al (2023) revealed that integrating a semi-military culture into daily school life—such as time discipline, neatness, and proactive attitudes—can shape students into individuals better prepared to face various challenges in the industrial world (Siburian et al., 2023). Their research indicates that students involved in programs using a semi-military approach show improvements in discipline and responsibility, which become valuable assets when they enter the workforce.

The implementation of a semi-military culture at SMKN 2 Sangatta Utara is integrated into all aspects of school life. Time discipline, neatness, and the development of students' attitudes and behaviors are the main focus in creating a conducive environment for character-building. This aligns with Sariwulan's (2020) findings, which state that a thoroughly integrated semi-military approach in school culture can strengthen students' character and enhance their readiness to enter the competitive job market (Sariwulan et al., 2020). This semi-military approach has been incorporated as a key part of the school's cultural management strategy at SMKN 2 Sangatta Utara. The strategy is designed to improve graduate quality, particularly in terms of discipline and work ethic, which are considered essential aspects to meet industrial demands. This is evident from school document data showing an increase in graduate absorption into the workforce. Research by Ali et al (2020) highlights that implementing school culture management oriented toward semi-military discipline can significantly improve student discipline (Ali et al., 2020). Their findings indicate that schools adopting this approach

successfully create a more orderly and structured environment, ultimately enhancing graduate quality.

Asiatico (2023), in his study on school culture management, stated that integrating a semi-military approach into school strategies not only fosters discipline but also strengthens students' work ethic (Asiatico, 2023). The research found that students involved in semi-military programs exhibit a higher commitment to their tasks and responsibilities, aligning with workplace expectations. This suggests that effective school culture management, focusing on discipline and work ethic, can better prepare students for the challenges of the industrial world. The objective of this article is to highlight the challenge of differing physical strength among students in the context of implementing a semi-military culture in schools. It emphasizes the need for adaptive policies that ensure inclusivity and prevent negative impacts on students with lower physical endurance while maintaining the benefits of discipline, responsibility, and mental resilience.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study uses a qualitative approach with a case study method to provide a comprehensive understanding of how the management of semi-military school culture contributes to shaping the disciplinary character of cadets, ultimately improving graduate quality. A qualitative approach was chosen to allow the researchers to explore the phenomenon deeply, providing rich insights into the impact of such a school culture on students. The case study method enables a focus on a specific context, SMK Negeri 2 Sangatta Utara, which has implemented this unique semi-military culture. By using this method, the study aims to understand the particularities of this approach in an educational setting, ensuring the findings are relevant and applicable to the specific case of SMK Negeri 2 Sangatta Utara.

The research was conducted over three months during the odd semester of the 2024/2025 academic year at SMK Negeri 2 Sangatta Utara, located in the North Sangatta District of East Kutai Regency, East Kalimantan Province. The data collection process involved various techniques, including direct observations, interviews with school staff and students, and document analysis. This combination of methods allowed the researchers to gain diverse perspectives on how the semi-military culture is being managed and its effects on student discipline. By analyzing these different forms of data, the study aims to offer a thorough evaluation of how the semi-military culture fosters student responsibility and improves educational outcomes at the institution.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Result

Based on interviews with informants, it was found that the planning of the semi-military school culture for shaping cadets' disciplinary character to improve graduate quality at SMK Negeri 2 Sangatta Utara begins with meetings involving the vice principals and teachers. During the annual meeting, held at the start of each academic year, a needs analysis is conducted to understand student characteristics, the specific needs of the school, and assess the school environment's readiness to adopt the semi-military approach. As stated by the principal in the following interview excerpt: *"We hold a meeting at the beginning of the academic year with the vice principals and teachers to align our perspectives and analyze the school's needs*

and environmental characteristics for implementing the semi-military culture." (Interview, Principal, 12/11/24).

Subsequently, a program and curriculum development phase follows. The principal, in collaboration with the vice principals, incorporates semi-military elements into the curriculum, such as marching drills, school regulations, and other physical activities. As stated by the vice principal in charge of cadet affairs: *"We implement the semi-military system from the moment students are accepted through the beret-awarding ceremony. In daily school life, this is reinforced through morning and afternoon assemblies, addressing students as 'Cadets' and 'Junior Cadets,' and enforcing strict rules regarding uniforms and student conduct."* (Interview, Vice Principal, 13/11/24).

Additionally, mandatory extracurricular programs, such as military training, scouting, and the Anti-Bullying Community (ABC), are introduced to support the semi-military school culture. As noted by one of the teachers: *"One of the ways we integrate the semi-military culture is through mandatory extracurricular activities like military training, scouting, and the Anti-Bullying Community."* (Interview, Teacher, 15/11/24).

In general, these findings indicate that well-planned and needs-based strategies form the foundation for the successful implementation of a semi-military school culture at SMK Negeri 2 Sangatta Utara.

Implementation of the Semi-Military Culture

The implementation of the semi-military culture at SMK Negeri 2 Sangatta Utara begins during the student orientation period with an event called Pembaretan (Beret-Awarding Ceremony). According to the principal: *"Pembaretan is a crucial symbolic event. It instills a sense of pride and responsibility from the start of orientation. Through this activity, students understand that they are entering an environment with high discipline standards."* (Interview, Principal, 12/11/24). The vice principal in charge of cadet affairs further explained that cadets are required to attend daily assemblies in the morning and afternoon. As he stated:

"Daily assemblies help instill discipline and punctuality. They are an important moment to convey information, reinforce school values, and strengthen the bond between students and staff." (Interview, Vice Principal, 13/11/24). The semi-military culture implementation is further reinforced through a strict supervision mechanism under the Disciplinary Commission's Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs). The vice principal explained: *"The Disciplinary Commission's SOP ensures that all disciplinary actions are taken fairly and consistently. This creates an orderly environment where students understand the consequences of their actions."* (Interview, Vice Principal, 13/11/24).

Additionally, the Control Book system is used to monitor students' discipline and behavior, as stated by the principal: *"The Violation Card and Achievement Card are effective monitoring tools. They provide immediate feedback to students regarding areas for improvement and accomplishments, encouraging them to continue progressing."* (Interview, Principal, 12/11/24). Teachers play a crucial role in this monitoring system, as explained by one of them: *"The Control Book is a highly useful tool. We use it to record daily observations of students' discipline and provide direct feedback. It also facilitates communication with parents."* (Interview, Teacher, 15/11/24).

Parent-School Communication

Effective communication between the school and parents is a key factor in the successful implementation of the semi-military culture. Parents provide valuable insights into their children's behavioral changes at home. One parent stated: "The Control Book helps us understand our child's behavior at school and how we can support them at home. It strengthens communication between the school and family, which is crucial for character-building." (Interview, Parent, 15/11/24). Another parent reinforced this by stating: "I have observed very positive changes. My child has become more disciplined and responsible at home. They also have a greater appreciation for time and rules, which is a result of the semi-military culture." (Interview, Parent, 15/11/24).

Discussion

Planning of the Semi-Military Culture

Planning is a systematic process of determining goals, strategies, and necessary steps to achieve the desired outcomes. In the context of education, planning plays a crucial role in setting the direction and policies that enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of both the learning process and students' character development (Setiyati et al., 2024). A well-structured planning process is the foundation for the successful implementation of educational programs, particularly those that integrate special cultural values, such as a semi-military approach. These findings align with several studies emphasizing the importance of planning in improving education quality and shaping student character. The annual school meeting at the beginning of the academic year serves as a fundamental step in ensuring that all school members understand the vision, mission, and objectives of the program (Husnurofik et al., 2024). Research by Anisah (2023) suggests that clear communication and coordination at the start of the academic year are key factors in the successful implementation of educational programs. In the context of semi-military culture, these meetings also serve as a platform for setting discipline standards and expectations (Anisah, 2023). In the context of semi-military culture, these meetings also serve as a platform for setting discipline standards and expectations. A needs and environmental analysis helps schools understand both internal and external conditions that influence program implementation. According to Sukendar (2019) needs analysis is essential to tailor programs to the specific requirements of students and their surroundings (Sukendar et al., 2019). By understanding these needs, schools can develop appropriate strategies to support character building and improve graduate quality. The integration of military-inspired programs into the curriculum represents an innovative educational approach. Furthermore, Research by Anisah (2023) states that incorporating specific values into the curriculum can enhance students' character education (Anisah, 2023). In this case, the discipline, responsibility, and leadership values promoted through the semi-military culture are expected to shape students with strong character.

In addition, the development of extracurricular activities supporting the military-oriented program also plays a significant role in providing practical experience for students. As described by Angraini (2023) participation in structured extracurricular activities can improve students' social skills, confidence, and discipline (Angraini et al., 2023). Well-designed extracurricular programs provide students with opportunities to apply the values they have learned in real-life situations. The introduction of a control book for students and parents serves

as an effective strategy for monitoring and evaluating student discipline. Parental involvement in their child's education through communication tools such as the control book can enhance student performance (Armadi et al., 2024; Mulawarman et al., 2021; Nur Rizkiyah, 2023). This book also strengthens school-family relationships, creating a supportive environment for character building.

Implementation of the Semi-Military Culture

The implementation of semi-military school culture at SMK Negeri 2 Sangatta Utara demonstrates a structured approach to fostering student discipline. The execution of various disciplinary activities and continuous supervision serves as a key element in this program. These findings align with research emphasizing the importance of consistency in implementing educational programs to achieve optimal outcomes. The application of semi-military culture, which includes routine activities and structured discipline assessments, reflects theory on character development through habituation. As stated by Sobri (2019), strong character is built through consistent habits, including appreciation for discipline and responsibility. Activities such as daily assemblies and achievement tracking reinforce these positive habits in students' daily lives (Sobri et al., 2019; W. Warman et al., 2024). Additionally, the use of evaluation tools such as violation cards and control books highlights the importance of continuous monitoring. Previous research suggests that ongoing formative assessment is a crucial factor in enhancing student performance. By regularly monitoring discipline and achievements, schools can provide constructive feedback to students and parents, which in turn encourages continuous improvement (Arif Nugraha et al., 2023; Warman et al., 2024). Parental involvement through the control book also demonstrates the importance of school-family partnerships in supporting character education. Angraini (2023) emphasizes that parental engagement in education is essential for strengthening learning at home. The control book serves as an effective communication tool, allowing parents to monitor and support their child's discipline development, ensuring consistency between home and school environments (Angraini et al., 2023). Overall, the implementation of the semi-military culture at SMK Negeri 2 Sangatta Utara illustrates how a systematic and consistent approach contributes to shaping disciplined students. Relevant research supports the importance of structured program execution that involves multiple stakeholders in achieving sustainable improvements in education quality.

CONCLUSION

The research highlights the crucial steps taken during the planning stage at SMK Negeri 2 Sangatta Utara. These steps laid the foundation for a semi-military school culture. The initial meeting at the start of the academic year was essential for setting goals and aligning all parties involved, including school staff, students, and parents. Conducting a needs and environmental analysis ensured that the school's approach was tailored to meet both the internal needs of students and the external demands of the surrounding environment. Developing a military-oriented program and integrating it into the curriculum was an innovative approach to instilling discipline and leadership. Additionally, extracurricular activities were carefully designed to reinforce these values, while creating control books for students and parents further promoted a partnership between the school and home in maintaining discipline.

During the implementation stage, various activities were executed to promote the values of discipline, responsibility, and character development. One of the significant events was the beret-awarding ceremony during orientation, which symbolized the cadets' commitment to the semi-military culture. Daily morning and afternoon assemblies provided an opportunity to reinforce these values consistently. The school followed strict Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) to ensure discipline was maintained, including recording violations in the Cadet Violation Card. This system was paired with the Cadet Achievement Card, where positive behaviors were documented, highlighting the importance of both accountability and recognition.

In addition to the formal activities, the research shows how the school provided students with control books to guide their behavior and discipline. These control books served as a tool for both students and parents, ensuring that discipline was not only monitored in school but also reinforced at home. By involving parents in this process, SMK Negeri 2 Sangatta Utara fostered a collaborative effort to build strong character and discipline. The structured approach to implementing the semi-military culture helped students develop leadership skills and a sense of responsibility, ultimately contributing to improved educational outcomes.

CONTRIBUTION STATEMENT

Agus Saputra: Research Concept, Methodology, Preparing the Original Manuscript. Widyatmike Gede Mulawarman: Data Curation. Warman: Data Curation, Data Analysis, Supervision. Nurlaili: Research Administration. Azainil: Data Analysis, Supervision. Laili Komariyah: Research Administration.

The authors declare that this manuscript has not been published previously and is not under consideration for publication in any journal. All authors have approved the publication of this manuscript, and if accepted, it will not be published elsewhere in the same form, in either Indonesian or any other language, including electronically, without the written consent of the copyright holder.

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